

Meeting 10 (Hybrid)
18-20 April 2023, Trondheim, Norway

Book of Abstracts

COST Action SAGA (CA17131) Final Meeting

Reflecting on the experience

Edited by Carmen Cuenca-Garcia, Arne Anderson Stamnes & Krzysztof Kiersnowski

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Scientific Programme

(Hybrid meeting, [contact the organisers](#) to attend online)

DAY 1

Tuesday 18 th April 2023			
VENUE: Suhmhuset Auditorium			
9:00	9:30	Morning coffee & registration	
9:30	09:35	Welcome to NTNU	
Introduction to the Workshop			
09:35	09:45	Objectives and Schedule	
09:45	09:55	LO communications	
Session 1: Integrated approaches to archaeology that combine geophysics and soil science to maximise proxy data interpretation. A) <i>Geophysical methods and soil analysis to assess contrast dynamics behind the detection of buried archaeological features.</i>			
10:00	10:10	STSM: An Overview after 4 years of activities.	Elina Aidona
10:15	10:25	Magnetism Of Neolithic Structures – A Special Focus on Possible Causes of Extremely High Magnetic Response (<i>STSM project</i>)	Neli Jordanova
10:30	10:40	The case of the missing ditches – a case study in the Po Valley, Italy (<i>STSM project</i>)	Kainz Jakob
10:45	10:55	Identifying geophysical, physical, and spectral soil properties of Brześć Kujawski culture traces in glacial soils of Kuyavia (Poland) (<i>STSM project</i>)	Jeroen Verhegge
11:00	11:30	Coffee Break with “1 Minute Pitch” poster presentations: 11:10 <i>Dreaming of Perfect Soil: Interactions between Soil and Geophysical Measurements for Archaeological Detection</i> by Michel Dabas (<i>STSM project</i>) 11:15 <i>On Formation of Magnetic Anomalies on Late Roman Cemeteries in the Forest-Steppe of Ukraine</i> by Kseniia Bondar (<i>STSM project</i>) 11:20 <i>Palaeochannels of the Rakhigarhi Hinterland in Haryana (India)</i> by Kishan Amarasinghe (online)	

DAY 1

		11:25 <i>Soils as proxy for late Quaternary paleoenvironmental evolution of the Yesha Valley (Naftali Mountains, Israel) by Hilit Kranenburg</i>	
<p>Session 1: Integrated approaches to archaeology that combine geophysics and soil science to maximise proxy data interpretation. <i>B) Geophysical methods and soil analyses to identify buried archaeological sites and assess past activity areas and paleoenvironments.</i></p>			
11:30	11:40	Soil Sampling and Mineral-Magnetic Characterisation to Improve Archaeo-Geophysical Interpretation. An Example of The Roman Site at Auritz/Aurizberri, Navarre (Spain) <i>(STSM & TS project)</i>	Garcia-Garcia Ekhine
11:45	11:55	Investigating The Domestic Functional and Social Activity Areas for Cucuteni Chalcolithic Sites from Ne Romania. Case Study: Dumbrăvita – Tarlăua Iezerul Settlement	Andrei Asandulesei
12:00	12:10	Archaeological remote sensing survey at the site of Tejada la Vieja (Escacena del Campo, Huelva): Correlating soil analysis and spectral signatures	David Villalón-Torres
12:15	12:25	Combining remote sensing and environmental sampling at transhumant shieling sites	Kristoffer Dahle
12:30	14:00	Lunch	
Session 2: Country-based overviews			
14:00	14:10	Brief History of the Development of Archaeo-geophysics in Slovakia	Roman Pasteka
14:15	14:25	State-of-the-art of ground-based geophysics for archaeological prospection and paleo-landscape studies in Denmark	Søren Kristansen
14:30	14:40	An Overview of Geoarchaeology Work in Republic of Srpska (Bosnia and Hercegovina)	Ivana Pandžić
14:45	14:55	Archaeo-geophysics used as a dating tool for ancient baked clays: The Italian experience	Evdokia Tema

15:00	15:45	<p>Coffee Break with "1 Minute Pitch" poster presentations:</p> <p>15:10 Magnetometric survey data and their testing by archaeological excavations in Poienesti-Lucaseuca culture settlements: preliminary results by Nicolai Batog</p> <p>15:15 Contribution of VLF Electromagnetic Survey to the Investigation of Ancient Mines In Hessdalen (Norway) by George Vargemezis</p> <p>15:20 Modelling Archaeological Environment and Geophysical Response Using Cesium Magnetometry in Roman Archaeological Site Argamum (Romania) by Sorin Anghel</p> <p>15:25 Using GPR Method For Archeological Propection. A Case Study in Kosturino, North Macedonia by Kemal Edip</p> <p>15:30 Depth Determination of Potential Archaeological Structures on Total Magnetic Anomaly Maps: Oluz Mound Example (Turkey) by Hazel Deniz Toktay</p>	
Session 3: Outcomes from Training Schools and other SAGA tools			
15:45	15:55	Science collaboration without borders - introducing large-scale GPR investigations in Finland (<i>STSM & VM project</i>)	Wesa Perttola
16:00	16:10	SAGA Training School 4 'ER and GPR Survey and related Geoarchaeological Methods' (10-17 April 2022, Valandovo, North Macedonia) (<i>TS project</i>)	Radomir Ivanovic
16:15	16:25	SAGA Training School 3 'Magnetic Laboratory Methods in Support of Archaeology' (Prague, 28-31 March 2022, Prague, Czech Republic) (<i>TS project</i>)	Hana Grison
16:30	16:45	Q&A and LO communications	
17:45	19:15	Organ concert at the Nidaros Cathedral by courtesy of the Trondheim City Council	
20:00		Dinner at <i>Hevd Restaurant</i> (please confirm to Ingrid Salvesen (ingrid.salvesen@ntnu.no) before 12th April 2023.	

DAY 2

Wednesday 19th April 2023			
VENUE: Suhmhuset Auditorium			
9:00	9:30	Morning coffee & registration	
SAGA Workshop (continuation)			
9:30	09:40	Welcome to Day 2	
Session 4: Modelling, Data Analysis, and Integration			
09:45	09:55	Know Your Enemy: Parameterising the Description of Noise in Geophysical Measurements for Archaeology (STSM project)	Armin Schmidt
10:00	10:10	1D/3D sensitivity analysis of low frequency electromagnetic method in archaeology for soils and features characterization: review and progress (STSM project)	François-Xavier Simon
10:15	10:25	Searching for innovative ways of data analysis in archaeological prospection (STSM projects)	Jan Horák
10:30	10:40	New statistical approaches to the integration of archaeological survey data (STSM project)	Richard Hewitt
10:45	11:15	Poster Coffee Break	
Session 5: Integrated proxy studies for site preservation, monitoring, evaluating risk for natural disasters/climate change.			
11:15	11:25	The CHERISH Toolkit: Applying earth sciences to monitor and understand the impacts of climate change on the cultural heritage of our seas and coasts	Robert Shaw
11:30	11:40	The importance of integrated geophysics in the determination of importantly deformed subsurface archaeological structures	Mahmut Drahor
11:45	11:55	Prospecting flooded stone ages sites. Multivariate geophysical proxies within a hydroelectric dam	Kristoffer Dahle
12:00	12:10	Understanding the cityscape of Soba by means of magnetometry and Ground-Penetrating Radar data	Robert Ryndziewicz

12:15	12:25	LO communications	
12:30	14:00	Lunch	
14:00	14:10	ORE presentation (online)	
Session 6: Upcoming Projects			
14:15	14:25	In search for the answers — geophysical research on the WWII extermination camps areas and excavation strategies at memorial sites	Sebastian Różycki
14:30	14:40	Investigating the Migration Period ringforts on Öland, Sweden with GPR.	Ellinor Hedberg
14:45	14:55	Uncovering the secrets of the Tumulus of Laona in Palaepaphos, Cyprus, through an integrated geophysical approach	Apostolos Sarris
15:00	15:10	Introducing SENSING IBERIANSCAPES – Exploration of indigenous settlements from the Iron Age on the Eastern coast of the Iberian Peninsula using minimal invasive strategies	Carmen Cuenca-Garcia
15:15	15:30	Q&A	
15:35	15:40	Winner of the poster competition PRIZE	
15:40	15:45	LO communications & Closure	
16:00	17:00	Visit to the Museum exhibition	
20:00		Dinner at <i>To Rom og Kjøkken</i> (please confirm to Ingrid Salvesen (ingrid.salvesen@ntnu.no) before 12th April 2023.	

Abstracts

SESSION 1

INTEGRATED APPROACHES TO ARCHAEOLOGY THAT COMBINE GEOPHYSICS AND SOIL SCIENCE

a) Geophysical methods and soil analysis to assess contrast dynamics behind the detection of buried archaeological features

Chair: Carmen CUENCA-GARCIA

1. STSM: AN OVERVIEW AFTER FOUR YEARS OF ACTIVITIES

[Elina AIDONA](#)¹, Kayt ARMSTRONG² and Carmen CUENCA-GARCIA³

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Short-term scientific missions (STSM) are exchange visits between researchers involved in a COST Action, allowing scientists to visit an institution or laboratory in another COST Member state. The aim of these scientific missions is to strengthen existing networks, foster collaboration in excellent research infrastructures and share new techniques that may not be available in a participant's home institution or laboratory. STSMs turned to be a successful procedure during SAGA years.

In total 31 researchers visited different laboratories and institutes. Even in pandemic years (2020-2021) several colleagues took advantage of the Virtual Mobility training. The maximum mobility was observed during Grant period 2 (July 2019-February 2020) and Grant period 4 (April 2022-October 2022). In the current talk an overview of the STSM grants will be presented. We will highlight the main scientific interests of the grantees and we will reveal the most popular host institution.

2. MAGNETISM OF NEOLITHIC STRUCTURES – A SPECIAL FOCUS ON POSSIBLE CAUSES OF EXTREMELY HIGH MAGNETIC RESPONSE

Neli JORDANOVA¹ and Jörg FASSBINDER²

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Magnetic prospection studies of Neolithic sites in Central and SE Europe, and laboratory mineral magnetic investigations on fired clay remains from the same epoch detect extremely high magnetisation values pertinent to this oldest period from the beginning of the agrarian-based human's evolution. Irrespective of the specific site's occupational history and location, very high concentration of strongly magnetic iron oxides, producing strong magnetic signal, is particularly characteristic to these sites. Systematic aerial archaeology survey and magnetometer prospecting results reveal a qualitatively darker colour of top soils and generally higher magnetic anomalies of archaeological features (e.g. ditches, pits, palisades or traces of wooden houses), as compared to similar features from the Bronze or Iron Age (Figure 1).

The aim of our study was to try answering the question if this effect is due to different climate conditions and/or to different behaviour or land use fire technique of Neolithic communities. This question was studied by involving multidisciplinary approach and combining magnetic prospection data and environmental magnetism. Rock-magnetic investigations of selected collection of burnt clay materials from Neolithic sites from Bulgaria and a Chalcolithic kiln, excavated in the Bora Plain (Iraqi Kurdistan) were carried out during the STSM of N. Jordanova to LMU Munich, hosted by J. Fassbinder.

Thermomagnetic analyses of high-temperature behaviour of saturation magnetization, hysteresis curves and back-field remanent magnetization measurements, acquisition curves of isothermal remanent magnetization were carried out during the STSM. Newly obtained data on samples from Bulgaria and Iraq give important information about the magnetic mineralogy and grain size of the iron oxides found in burnt clay from the Neolithic sites. The main magnetic mineral identified was magnetite with $T_c \sim 580^\circ\text{C}$. Hysteresis curves and back-field DC curves were used to construct the Day diagram, showing generally presence of stable PSD magnetic grains. Laboratory step-wise IRM acquisition curves demonstrate the dominant role of the magnetically soft minerals in combination with a higher coercivity phase, most probably related to the presence of fine-grained hematite. The results obtained will be discussed in relation to different environmental factors.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu).

References

Kovacheva, M., Kostadinova-Avramova, M., Jordanova, N., Lanos, P., Boyadzhiev, Y., 2014. Extended and revised archaeomagnetic database and secular variation curves from Bulgaria for the last

eight millennia. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* 236, 79–94.

Squitieri, A. Amicone, S. Dinckal, A. Altaweel, M. Gur-Arieh, S. Rohde, J. Herr, J.-J., Pietsch, S. Miller, M. (2022) A Multi-Method Study of a Chalcolithic Kiln in the Bora Plain (Iraqi Kurdistan): The Evidence From Excavation, Micromorphological and Pyrotechnological Analyses. *Open Archaeology* 2022; 8: 853–872, <https://doi.org/10.1515/opar-2022-0265>

Figure 1: (Left) Steinabrunn, Austria. Magnetogram of the Neolithic ring ditch enclosure. The ditch is filled by topsoil, the palisades and a pit in the center of the enclosure show up as a normal positive (black) anomaly. (Right) Holzen, Bavaria, Magnetogram of the Iron Age ditch enclosure. The ditch is filled by topsoil, but the palisades and a pit in the center of the enclosure also show up as a normal positive (black) anomaly. Both archaeological sites consist of similar constructions such like ditches, palisade and wooden posts, on similar loess-soils. The intensity of magnetic anomalies however differs by factor 2-3.

Figure 2: Examples of thermomagnetic analyses for samples from Neolithic sites from Bulgaria (a- site Kovachevo dated ~5800 BC; b- site Popovo dated ~5300 BC (Kovacheva et al., 2014)) and Iraq (b & c) (Chalcolithic Kiln in the Bora Plain (Iraqi Kurdistan)). Bold curve – heating, thin line – cooling.

3. THE CASE OF THE MISSING DITCHES – A CASE STUDY IN THE PO VALLEY, ITALY

Jakob KAINZ

University of Vienna

For a geophysical prospection project in the central Po Valley, and in cooperation with the Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio for the provinces of Cremona, Lodi and Mantova, Italy various sites were surveyed with magnetometry and GPR. The geophysical surveys revealed an abundance of archaeology across sites ranging from the Bronze Age to the Middle Ages, including Bronze Age burial mounds and settlements, a Roman kiln and warehouse site, a couple of Roman villa sites and a multiperiod site dating from the Roman to medieval period. At the sites of Casalromano and Asola Saccole there are clearly visible tumulus in the aerial photographs however only at Asola Saccole are these also visible in the magnetometry data (Figure 1). At Casalromano a plethora of features are visible in the aerial photography however only a minority of these is visible in the magnetometry data whilst a GPR survey revealed numerous further features (Figure 2).

To understand why many of the identified features are not visible the magnetometry data samples, from coring and during an excavation, were collected at both sites. This allowed targeting numerous features that are visible and invisible, especially in the magnetometry data.

The samples were measured for their mass magnetic susceptibility, frequency dependent magnetic susceptibility, hysteresis loop, IRM, DC demagnetisation remanence (DCD) and PXRF at the Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Science, Prague. This allowed assessing the usability of the applied geophysical methods, especially regarding the different geographic and archaeological settings. This helped quantifying soil properties of archaeological and non-archaeological areas and features, through using complementary field and laboratory methods, which helped identify specific parameters of visible and invisible features within the magnetometry data.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu). It was also supported by the INTER-EXCELLENCE program of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (MEYS), grant No. LTC19029.

Figure 1: The site of Asola Saccole with the clearly visible tumuli ditches.

Figure 2: The site of Casalromano with the magnetometry, GPR, excavation and aerial photography data and varying degrees of the visibility for archaeological features.

4. IDENTIFYING GEOPHYSICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL SOIL PROPERTIES OF BRZEŚĆ KUJAWSKI CULTURE TRACES IN GLACIAL SOILS OF KUYAVIA

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3 University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland

4 Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland

The Neolithic Brześć Kujawski culture of the Polish lowlands is characterized by large settlements with trapezoidal longhouses, known from aerial photography and excavations. However, these are hardly detectable by magnetometer survey. Nevertheless, captured crop marks suggest that, at least temporarily, moisture contrasts, and thus potentially electrical and/or dielectric permittivity contrasts, may occur.

This was investigated in Radojewice (site no. 29) through frequency domain electromagnetic induction survey (EMI, Dualem 21Hs), ground penetrating radar (GPR, ImpulseRadar Raptor45) and electrical resistance survey (RES, Geoscan RM85). These complemented the existing fluxgate gradiometer data (MAG, Sensys MXV3) (Figure 1-left). Furthermore, two small test trenches were excavated, cross-sectioning two longhouse features, both responsive and unresponsive to the magnetometer survey. The wall feature and background soil of the latter were investigated extensively through in situ profile measurements (SM-30, Hydraprobe) and bulk sampling (Figure 1-top right).

The profile measurements (Figure 1-bottom right) revealed a soil moisture, electrical conductivity and dielectric permittivity contrast between the loamy archaeological fill and the sands of the natural (ferro-)humic podzol. Explaining why the longhouse signal was missing in the EMI ECa but present in the GPR and RES requires further investigation. The surveys and excavations also revealed that the spatial variation in the appearance of crop marks was closely related to lower ECa zones in local depressions where the preservation of a sandy E-horizon creates differential vegetation stress whereas this horizon was probably ploughed out elsewhere. Magnetic susceptibility (MS) data illustrate that the magnetic variation in the natural soil profile is much more significant than in the longhouse's wall profile. Hence, natural variations in soil magnetic properties might appear more pronounced than archaeological variations. In concordance, higher EMI IP-MS zones are also interpreted as areas with a thicker humic B horizon in absence of an E horizon, since such soil sequence was observed in trench 2.

In conclusion, the variable preservation of the podzol horizons seems to control the geophysical and spectral signals at the site.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu).

Figure 1: (Left) Main map: locations of the areas surveyed with the different methods. Background: NIR drone orthophoto; Inset map top right: Location of trench 1 over non-magnetic house feature. Background: magnetometer survey data (± 3 nT, black positive)(left), NIR drone orthophoto detail (right); Inset map bottom left: Location of trench 2 over magnetic house feature. Background: magnetometer survey data (left), NIR drone orthophoto detail (right). (Top right) Orthofoto from the trench 1 with locations of the profile measurements and retrieved samples. (Bottom right) SM-30 (MS) and Hydraprobe data of the archaeological and natural profile in trench 1.

5. DREAMING OF PERFECT SOIL: INTERACTIONS BETWEEN SOIL AND GEOPHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS FOR ARCHAEOLOGICAL DETECTION

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³ *University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus*

The soil constitutes in most cases the matrix in which the archaeological remains are buried and protected. For these structures to be detectable, archaeo-geophysicists know that there must be one or more contrasts in physical properties between the soil and the structures. But much more rarely are considered two other factors: the spatial structure of the soil and/or its surface condition.

However, these intrinsic factors greatly influence the detection of buried heritage. Their consideration is just as important as that of the contrasts mentioned above. These factors will not have the same consequences depending on the types of geophysical methods used and even depending on the type of device used, as will be show by a certain number of examples. Electrical (as well as electrostatic) methods are primarily related to the water content of the soil as much as its texture or structure. For example, in the case of

cryosols, the cryoturbation that may have appeared during and after the last glaciations leads to the formation of polygons. The example below comes from a survey we have carried out at Pierrelaye in the Parisian sedimentary basin in 2008 (Figure 1).

The geophysical image of these structures is very complex and often prevents the detection of archaeological structures as found for example in certain parts of the site of Vieil-Evreux in Normandy (Schmidt et al., 2020, fig. 15). More generally, any significant spatial variability of soils at short wavelength will be unfavorable to detection of the majority of archaeological structures (shallow soils, soils whose substrate is very fractured or dissolved, polygonal soils, some alluvial soils, sand blown deposits, etc.). Even if the physical factors are preponderant in prospecting, it also happens that chemical factors play an important role: for example, the accumulation of livestock in certain fields modifies the conductivity very strongly and locally. We were able to demonstrate this on the archaeological site of Wroxeter in England (Dabas et al., 2000, p. 115).

For magnetic methods, it is above all the oxidation/reduction mechanisms of the magnetic components of the soil that will create different responses depending on the water and oxygen contents as well as the ferrous oxide compositions. As for electrical prospecting, we might also point out the case of soils with very high magnetic responses and whose spatial variability is intrinsically very high. Apart from soils developed over volcanic or metamorphic materials, alluvial soils even in sedimentary basins may contain many magnetic boulders preventing an easy detection of archaeological structures (Figure 2). For high frequency electromagnetic methods (GPR), the clay content is one of the parameters controlling the penetration of the electromagnetic wave. We observed that even lowering the antenna center frequency does not improve the penetration of the radar wave in this case. Research remains to be done depending on the type of clay. The presence also of diffracting structures, often linked to a particular soil texture, will, as for the other methods, create a noise which will be superimposed on the archaeological signal. However, this noise can be reduced by lowering the frequency of the antennas used.

In summary, the examples selected have shown the influence of soil on the ability to detect buried archaeological structures. These are parameters on which it is difficult or even impossible to intervene. On the other hand, a better knowledge of these interactions would make it possible to better predict the response of buried archaeological structures. This knowledge must be based on a mapping of a set of key physical and chemical properties of soils on a sufficient spatial scale to be exploitable by archaeo-geophysicists.

References

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Figure 1: Electrical surveys (ARP with 3 depths of investigation (a) 0 to 0.5m; (b) 0 to 1 m; (c) 0 to 1.7m; (d) Morphological characteristics of periglacial structures; from Van Ort et al., 2013, p.12 & 15).

Figure 1: Magnetic response over the gallic oppidum of Gondole (a) magnetic map scale -50 to 50 nT/m, (b) aerial interpretation and results from excavations (from Y. Deberge and Dabas, p. 288 & 290).

6. ON FORMATION OF MAGNETIC ANOMALIES ON LATE ROMAN CEMETERIES IN THE FOREST-STEPPE OF UKRAINE

Kseniia BONDAR¹, Jörg W. E. FASSBINDER², Serhii DIDENKO³ and Sandra E. HAHN²

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2 Geophysics Dept. Ludwig-Maximilians University of Munich, Munich, Germany

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This study involves rock magnetic and magnetic mineralogy examinations of infill from burials comparing to background soil to answer what factors are responsible for formation of measurable magnetic anomalies on Late Roman cemeteries of Chernyakhiv-Sântana de Mureş culture in the Forest-Steppe of Ukraine.

On the total field magnetic map the destroyed inhumations appear as low-intensive (2-4 nT) anomalies (Figure 1A,B). Intact inhumations and cremations do not appear on magnetic maps. Infill of destroyed inhumations demonstrates great similarity to the topsoil in magnetic phase mineralogy and properties. Curie temperatures and phase transformation observed during measurements of the thermal dependence of the magnetization on topsoil and infill samples are the same. The topsoil of background chernozem-like soils hosts maximum concentrations of superparamagnetic-single domain (SP-SD) grains, which is evidenced by maximal values of concentration-dependent magnetic parameters. This may suggest pedogenic origin of the SP-SD component. We also have good preservation of SD fractions in the infill of burials. The magnetic susceptibility and natural remanence of the infill has the same values as the topsoil, Keonigsberger ratio of the infill of burials, as well as of the topsoil, is close to 1, and close to 0.5 for loess (Figure 1C).

Forward modelling of destroyed burials revealed a good correspondence of calculated and observed field when layers of magnetic source model are assigned with magnetization equal to difference between magnetization of the feature and the surrounding soil/subsoil layer (Figure 1D). SD grains are characterized by the ability to orient towards the ambient magnetic field under conditions of sufficient moisture. The sediment acquires detrital magnetization arising from the collective alignment with the Earth's magnetic field of small magnetic carriers. That means, the grave infill could acquire total magnetization of the same intensity as the topsoil in case of gradual refilling of a pit with predominantly topsoil material aided by atmospheric precipitation.

This leads to the conclusion on the way of treating the destroyed burials by Chernyakhiv-Sântana de Mureş culture people: a pit left open and the topsoil material gradually re-filled it. It could presumably happen in case of abandoned burials` looting. The described mechanism is applicable to the origin of anomalies of a large variety of archaeological features like ditches, dugouts, catacombs etc.

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This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu).

Figure 1: Figure 1. Example of Komariv cemetery: magnetic map(A), excavated graves and sampled background soil section(B) and measured magnetic properties (C), magnetic model and calculated field (D).

INTEGRATED APPROACHES TO ARCHAEOLOGY THAT COMBINE GEOPHYSICS AND SOIL SCIENCE

b) Geophysical methods and soil analyses to identify buried archaeological sites and assess past activity areas and paleoenvironments.

Chair: Apostolos SARRIS

7. SOIL SAMPLING AND MINERAL-MAGNETIC CHARACTERISATION TO IMPROVE ARCHAEO-GEOPHYSICAL INTERPRETATION. AN EXAMPLE OF THE ROMAN SITE AT AURITZ/AURIZBERRI, NAVARRRE (SPAIN)

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Geophysical and geoarchaeological methods have been used extensively to delimit and characterise the Roman site of Zaldua, located in the NE of Navarre (Garcia-Garcia et al. 2016; 2017). Although the results of those surveys provide a firm basis for an archaeological assessment of the site, in some parts of the study area the geophysical response was difficult to interpret.

In summer 2019 the site hosted the First SAGA Training School, where main objective was to provide a clear methodological understanding of routine geophysical and soil science methods used in archaeological investigations. The hands-on sessions provide complementary data, but it became obvious that a deeper investigation of soil properties was needed in areas that pose difficulties in terms of their archaeo-geophysical interpretation. Therefore, a Short Time Scientific Mission (STSM) was conducted, with the main aim to improve in-situ measurements using soil magnetic characteristics to understand the factors affecting the geophysical results. Sampling was performed using a hand-held coring ma-

chine (Van Walt window corer equipped with a Cobra TT engine). The length of the cores was from 80 to 100 cm, divided into samples with a span of 1cm to 10cm, depending on the changes along the soil profile.

Laboratory measurements were done at the Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Science, Prague, Czech Republic. Magnetic susceptibility (MS) at different frequencies was measured by using Kappabridge MFK1-FA (AGICO, Brno, Czech Republic). The frequency-dependent magnetic susceptibility ($\chi_{FD}\%$) has been calculated to quantify pedogenic contribution. In order to identify magnetic grain size and mineral composition, the hysteresis and remanence characteristics were determined by using a Vibrating-sample magnetometer (ADE Corporation, VSM EV9 VSM 2900). Data were subsequently evaluated in a Day plot (Day et al., 1977).

Here we present the investigations focused on the north of the site, where a narrow area without magnetic contrast separates two zones with clear evidences of intensive occupation. Investigations show a homogeneous distribution of the MS and $\chi_{FD}\%$ data which suggest similar pedogenic influence. Within the rim area, with low magnetic contrast, the pedogenesis has been somehow limited. Moreover, the hysteresis parameters show a notable difference for the core located inside the fringe without magnetic contrast. The high coercivity component combined to low susceptibility suggests the existence of other magnetic minerals rather than magnetite. Those observations could be explained by waterlogging in the fringe, rendering an environment in which iron (hydro)oxides could transform into hard coercivity goethite (Cornell and Schwertmann, 2003). The applied methodology allowed improving the understanding of the main magnetic differences across the site. The lack of magnetic contrast is explained by the presence of higher water level at the fringe. Therefore, it can be preliminarily concluded that the fringe has been generated to avoid inconvenient terrain conditions, and not to mark a difference between the two occupation areas.

Acknowledgments

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8. INVESTIGATING THE DOMESTIC FUNCTIONAL AND SOCIAL ACTIVITY AREAS FOR CUCUTENI CHALCOLITHIC SITES FROM NE ROMANIA. CASE STUDY: DUMBRĂVITA – TARLAUA IEZERUL SETTLEMENT

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Through a recent research project aimed at a deeper analysis of the Chalcolithic settlements belonging to the Cucuteni culture (4600 to 3600/3500 cal. BC) in NE Romania, several archaeological sites were investigated in order to obtain information regarding their planimetry. Using, in particular, magnetometer measurements – due to a very good contrast of the burned structures specific to these communities – 25 cucutenian sites were investigated.

Preliminary data suggest careful territorial arrangement, both in the case of small and larger settlements, as well as obvious differences between certain case studies, in terms of internal spatial organization. In particular, variations were observed regarding the dimensions, orientation and organization of domestic or fortification/delimitation structures, as well as in the case of the distribution of open areas within the settlement. Additionally, it seems that the presence of an extension of habitation outside the main fortification/delimitation works is becoming clearer.

A representative example in this regard is the Dumbrăvita - Tarlaua Iezerul site (Figure 1). The geophysical results revealed the presence of a large cucutenian settlement (15 ha) with numerous well-defined archaeological structures (burnt dwellings, pits, kilns, ditches). More than 200 systematized dwelling structures have been identified, generally in rows, but also in groups, surrounded by ditches. A peculiarity of the Dumbrăvita settlement is its location in the vicinity of a lacustrine micro-depression with an area of about 10 ha, which practically marks the eastern limit of the settlement.

The archaeological excavation undertaken in June 2022 had as its objective the verification of a large magnetic anomaly, which suggested a dwelling with an area of around 200 square meters. The trench was placed transversally on the quasi-rectangular anomaly, capturing, as expected, the burned remains of a cucutenian dwelling of very large size compared to the known average (Figure 1).

The field investigations carried out for this site also considered two soil profiles, which were morphologically described and sampled on the northern profile of the archaeological trench (Figure 2). The first profile was opened in the vicinity of the researched dwelling, while the second intersected its central part. The maximum depth reached was 130 cm, from the present surface level. In the case of both profiles, the presence of a deep humic horizon, with very dark colours (10YR 2/1), was found, from the surface to the prehistoric dwelling level, also including the cultural layer. From a depth of about 75 cm, a marly material rich in calcium carbonate with a very fine texture appeared. Although the anthropic impact was decisive in the evolution of these soils, the morphological and physico-chemical characteristics indicate their evolution on former Calcaric Chernic Phaeozems corresponding to the Chalcolithic level. The clay texture and excessive content of calcium car-

bonates are factors that greatly limit, to the point of exclusion, the natural establishment of forest vegetation on such soils. Thus, we can assume that the existence of an open land, with a soil rich in organic matter in the top horizon, which could have facilitated extensive agricultural activities, constituted one of the premises for the location of these communities in the area.

Future research aims to expand such point-based pedological surveys for the entire surface of the site, targeting the areas near dwellings, (where we often find numerous pits of various types: garbage pits, for clay extraction, storage pits), parts on the route of access ways or from inside small open areas described by some groups of houses. By integrating the geophysical measurements with soil data, we want to better understand the functional units of the site in order to formulate new hypotheses regarding the social structure model of these communities.

Acknowledgments

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Figure 1: Dumbrăvita, Tarlaua lezerul - magnetic map and the archaeological trench from 2022 (top right).

Figure 2: Dumbrăvita, Tarlaua lezerul – soil profiles located near the excavated dwelling (left) and on the center of the archaeological structure (right).

9. CONTRIBUTION OF VLF ELECTROMAGNETIC SURVEY TO THE INVESTIGATION OF ANCIENT MINES IN HESSDALEN (NORWAY)

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An important task for the archaeological survey in global scale, is the exploitation of mineral deposits and extraction of the special minerals such as iron in ancient times. In Hessdalen area (Norway) geological setting is favourable for the generation of mineral deposits rich in zinc, iron and copper. Mining operation in the area was active till the decade of '80s but mineral deposits were already exploited by the Vikings, who were manufacturing their armory in the area. Melting of minerals to extract iron was done in furnaces resulting to the production of slag heap. The location of these areas can be detected by magnetic or electromagnetic methods, which are sensitive to this kind of material.

VLF surveys have been performed in Hessdalen valley during four wide geophysical field campaigns. VLF measurements have been carried out on a 20m average spacing along a large number of traces totaling 100km length (Figure 1). Among other geophysical measurements, the VLF method is applied in order to detect superficial conductive zones emerging at the ground surface, related either to tectonic features or to mineral deposits since small opened mines from Vikings age exist in the area.

Raw and filtered data along profiles are shown in Figures 2a and 2b. Grey areas indicate the conductive zones. Then, data were inverted in order to get resistivity models (Santos et al., 2006). The value of 1000 Ohmm was used as a typical for the bedrock and the color scale is designed that way that areas of resistivity values less than 1000 Ohmm represent conductive zones.

The resistivity model of the VLF profile chosen as an example is presented in Figure 2c. Basic processing of the field data (Fraser filtering) revealed conductive zones, mainly located on the limits of the geological formations of the area surrounding the intrusive gabbro formation which dominates the center of the valley. A part of the conductive zones has been found to be related with mineral deposits (mainly sulphites). The distribution of these conductive reveals an ellipse of 6x12 km dimensions related with the anticline in the area. Detection of possible ancient mining activity as well as location of furnaces can be further examined by the extension of VLF measurements as well with other geophysical methods (total magnetic field, self potential, resistivity and induced polarization).

Figure 1: Simplified geological map of the Hessdalen valley and surrounding area (modified from <http://geo.ngu.no/kart>).

Figure 2: (a) Raw data, (b) Fraser filtered data, (c) resistivity model of a VLF profile.

10. ARCHAEOLOGICAL REMOTE SENSING SURVEY AT THE SITE OF TEJADA LA VIEJA (ESCACENA DEL CAMPO, HUELVA): CORRELATING SOIL ANALYSIS AND SPECTRAL SIGNATURES

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We present the progress of our research line regarding to the identification and delimitation of archaeological sites through remote sensing. More specifically, the objective is to explore the possibilities of remote sensing with hyperspectral images from the PRISMA mission to identify chemical elements on the surface that can be related to an anthropogenic origin in the archaeological context of the site of Tejada la Vieja (Escacena del Campo, Huelva).

This site is one of the most outstanding archaeological sites in the protohistory of the Iberian Peninsula and, of course, one of the most significant in southern Spain. It dates from the Tartessian-Turdetan period, with an occupation that began around the 9th century BC, linked to mining, and ended in the 4th century BC. The site covers an area of 6.4 hectares, occupying a small elevation at an altitude of 170 m above sea level. It is well communicated with the Guadalquivir and the coast by river, as well as by land with Berrocal and Riotinto, linking the Tierra Llana with the Sierra of Huelva when crossing the Pata del Caballo through the pass of La Garganta.

Through this research we are trying to advance several working hypotheses: (1) It is possible to trace human activity in space and time, according to its impact and alteration of the environment where it has settled. (2) There is a persistent soil contamination over time of both organic and inorganic elements associated with historical anthropic activity. (3) We can improve the identification, characterisation and delimitation of archaeological sites by combining different remote sensing techniques in an efficient and non-destructive way.

In this paper we present the methodology used and the preliminary results of analysing 180 soil samples from the site under study, with a double objective: to characterise the surface of the site from a chemical and radiometric point of view, and to look for correlations that allow us to establish objective criteria to delimit and characterise the limits of anthropic activity associated with the site.

11. COMBINING REMOTE SENSING AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLING AT TRANSHUMANT SHIELING SITES

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The Scandinavian shieling system is well documented through ethnography and represents an important characteristic of traditional upland and outfield landscapes. Yet, the archaeological record of shielings and other transhumant sites is sparse, both due to their distant location, ephemeral structures and scarce material culture, but also due to later disturbances, inadequate methods and limited focus within archaeological research and management.

In 2022, a range of non-invasive methods (LiDAR, Photogrammetry, Thermal photography, Magnetic Susceptibility, Magnetometer, Ground Penetrating Radar) were employed at a selection of shieling sites, in order to shed light on their physical structure and archaeological potential. In this paper, I will present the results from the remote sensing, discussing the possibilities and limitations of various methods, and my plan for opening trial trenches – both in order to “verify” my prospection results and to do environmental sampling (C14, micromorphology, pXRF, aDNA, lipids, palaeobotany). In the end, I will suggest a step-by-step approach to identifying, delimiting and examining Prehistoric and Medieval shieling sites, combining both visual surveys, remote sensing and environmental sampling.

Acknowledgments

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12. SOILS AS PROXY FOR LATE QUATERNARY PALEOENVIRONMENTAL EVOLUTION OF THE YESHA VALLEY (NAFTALI MOUNTAINS, ISRAEL)

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The Yesha Valley is an elongated (1.8 km) and narrow (<0.1 km) N-S trending tectonic depression in the Naftali mountains. It follows a marginal fault of the Hula pull-apart basin and

is incised into the Dir Hannah Formation. It is drained eastward by 3 slope-channels and the Nahal Kadesh stream to the south. The Yesha Valley serves as an active subsiding local base level and a disturbance for channel flow and sediment transport to the Hula Valley. Sediments that accumulate in the valley include mostly reddish clays of Terra Rossa origin and aeolian dust.

The aim of the study is to analyse the sedimentary sequence in order to reconstruct the regional paleoenvironment and the later tectonic phases along the Yesha marginal fault. A 20 m long core of reddish clay sediments was extracted, down to the underlying limestone at the bottom of the valley. The analyses comprise visual sedimentological description, physical (magnetic susceptibility, GSD), mineralogy and chemical (XRF, XRD, TOC) and spectroscopy (FTIR). Chronology is based on luminescence dating.

Four different sedimentological segments were described (from the top): Segment A - 4.1 m thick, is composed of dark reddish clay, where the uppermost 3 m are significantly affected by agriculture. Segment B - 2.4 m thick, dated to about 85 ± 4 ky, is composed of brownish clay, rich in organic material, implying on a moist environment. Segment C - 8.5 m thick, is composed of relatively uniform red-dish-brown quartz-rich sediments dated to between 271 ± 18 and 767 ± 65 ky. The high Si content suggests large aeolian dust contribution. Segment D - 4.5 m thick, comprises 5 well-cemented calcic horizons (calcrete) older than 767 ± 65 ky. These calcic horizons indicate periods of tectonic quiescence, stability and pedogenesis in somewhat drier climate conditions. The intervals of clay units between the calcic horizons possibly indicate on tectonic subsidence phases. The relatively constant rate of accumulation of segments A-C is 17.209 mm/ky average, suggesting similar rates of tectonic gradual subsidence (creep).

SESSION 2

COUNTRY-BASED OVERVIEWS

Chair: Andrei AȘĂNDULEȘI

13. BRIEF HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARCHAEO-GEO-PHYSICS IN SLOVAKIA

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The beginnings of the application of geophysical methods in archaeological prospection in Slovakia can be dated to 1960s and 1970s, when we formed part of Czechoslovakia. At this time, simple DC resistivity measurements were performed with the aim of detecting the remains of old walls (e.g. location of medieval church building foundations). A great milestone was achieved by purchasing a Cs-vapour magnetometer in the Institute of Archaeology, Slovak Academy of Sciences in Nitra. Research was focused mainly on the mapping of roundels (Neolithic circular enclosures) (Tirpák 1997, Tirpák 2007). Among tens of sites, it is worthy to mention the Golianovo site (close to Nitra), where one of the largest roundel structures in central Europe was detected (3 ditches, 6 entrances, diameter: 200 m). Magnetometric research at that time was carried out in conjunction with the analysis of aerial photographs, which together helped to focus on selected parts of the landscape (e.g., Kuzma 2007). At the present time, magnetic gradiometry is widely used, the portfolio of sites is much larger – from settlements, to burial sites, tumuli, post holes, building remains etc.

In surveys of interiors of historical buildings (churches, castles, etc.) for detection of underground cavities (crypts, cellars, tunnels) Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) has been used only during the last few decades. In the period from 1970s to the Millennium GPR technology was not very accessible, because it was too expensive and only a few institutions could purchase this type of instrument. This has partly led to the development of the microgravity method for the detection of cavities. Strongly motivated by some pioneer works from Polish and Czech geophysicists, several churches were surveyed by this specialised non-de-

structive method. The method has been developed mainly in the area of data processing, and there exists several important sub-surface features, which have been found thanks to it (Pašteka et al. 2022).

In the last two decades, the application of archaeogeophysical methods has been intensively developed, motivated by successful applications worldwide, mainly in western Europe. A summary of results from the last few years, combined with data from Aerial Laser Scanning was presented in a monograph by Felcanová et al. (2021). In the coming years we see a great opportunity for the application of new data acquisition methods (e.g., three components EM). The variety of archaeological sites is extensive in Slovakia and there is a great opportunity for the application of new archaeogeophysical methods.

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14. STATE-OF-THE-ART OF GROUND-BASED GEOPHYSICS FOR ARCHAEOLOGICAL PROSPECTION AND PALEO-LANDSCAPE STUDIES IN DENMARK

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This paper presents the current status of geophysical methods in Denmark and outlines the state-of-the-art approach based on recent case studies. As recent developments in hardware and real-time-corrected positioning have made fast and accurate geophysical data acquisition feasible, this provides interesting, new venues for archaeological prospecting and paleo-landscape understanding.

In Denmark, however, the lack of in-house equipment, expertise and experience has ham-

SESSION 2

pered a proper application and acceptance for integrating geophysical data in archaeological projects. Still, within the last decade, some exciting results and development have led to new and promising applications (Stamnes et al., In press).

The presented cases are as follows: Utilizing electromagnetic induction through dedicated processing and inversion schemes to ensure non-biased soil structures can improve interpretation of the geological settings around archaeological sites. This scheme has been used to resolve palaeo channels (Christiansen et al., 2016), in situ preservation management solutions (Tjellden et al., 2016), and Viking Age fortification mapping (Kristiansen et al., 2022).

Better integration of geophysics into research, curatorial and developer funded practice, has recently been achieved using fluxgate gradiometry with an emphasis on intensive small-scale investigations in areas inaccessible to motorised arrays such as woodland, protected cultural and natural heritage sites. Successful examples include surveys of megalithic tombs funerary cairns and fortifications in woodland.

Towed magnetometer arrays provide a rapid and effective means of identifying both ferrous objects such as tools or weapons, as well as earth materials such as clays that have been fired in a kiln. These instruments, specifically the 8-gradiometer array system tMag from Aarhus University, have been successfully applied in a variety of locations such as Ørregård (Kass et al. 2021) and Fæsted. Unfortunately, the lack of accessible software for detailed interpretation often prevents the full use of the available information in the data.

As part of the research project PastCoast (Stamnes 2022), a series of Danish coastal sites known from historical investigations and metal detecting finds only have been investigated with large-scale, high-resolution ground penetrating radar and magnetometer surveys. These involve the sites of Lundeborg and Strandby on Fyn, as well as the sites of Langelands gaarde and Vester Vandet in northern Jutland. One of the aims is better to understand the deposition history of the archaeological objects and investigate if subsoil features detectable by geophysical methods can explain their spatial distribution. In addition, the data will be used to understand the palaeotopography and landscape formation better.

Finally, based on these cases we discuss how the recent developments of hardware and software, and dedicated data processing, for archaeo-geophysics prospection can make some or all the discussed instruments acceptable as standard methods within Danish cultural heritage management.

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15. AN OVERVIEW OF GEOARCHAEOLOGY WORK IN THE REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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This report presents the findings of the several years of geoarchaeological fieldwork and research conducted mostly in the region of the lower Vrbas River, Republic of Srpska (Bosnia and Herzegovina), as well as the findings of a pilot study investigating the type and origin of raw materials used for stone tool production during early prehistoric times.

Starting from 2009, when the overall scientific goals were set, the geoarchaeological investigations included systematic field-walking and augering surveys to establish landscape change sequences with respect to the archaeological record, checking for the potential existence of new archaeological sites and gathering data on their environmental setting. This was followed at a later stage by test excavations and sampling of some of the most promising sites.

So far, potential lithic source locations and materials have been investigated through field reconnaissance and laboratory testing conducted on excavated and museum-held stone tools using a variety of geological techniques (e.g. microscopy for mineralogical analyses), which are aiming at filling an important documentary gap that exists in the archaeological archives. All research has been done in cooperation between the PI Museum of the Republic of Srpska B&H and the McBurney Laboratory, Department of Archaeology, University of Cambridge, UK.

16. ARCHAEOGEOPHYSICS AS A DATING TOOL FOR ANCIENT BAKED CLAYS: THE ITALIAN EXPERIENCE

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Geophysical methods applied in archaeology are nowadays widely used both as non-destructive prospection surveys to detect underground archaeological remains as well as archaeomagnetic investigations to study the technology and chronological frame of archaeological findings. In fact, archaeological soils and baked clay artifacts that have experienced heating at high temperatures can acquire a strong and stable Thermal Remanent Magnetization (TRM) during their cooling in the presence of the ancient geomagnetic field. Such TRM can then be used for dating their last firing after comparison with local secular variation (SV) curves. In Italy, during the last decades great efforts have been done in order to establish archaeomagnetic dating as a powerful dating tool for ancient baked clays. Such efforts are focused both on the investigation of the magnetic properties

and archaeomagnetic record of in situ archaeological structures and pottery as well as on the construction of a detailed and reliable reference SV curve. Recently, a compilation of Italian archaeomagnetic data from both archaeological material and volcanic rocks has been published, permitting the calculation of directional and intensity SV curves that cover the last three millennia and make possible archaeomagnetic dating based on the full geomagnetic field vector.

Here, results of several case studies are presented, including integrated studies and comparison with dating results obtained from other dating techniques. Moreover, the contribution of the archaeointensity record on improving the archaeomagnetic dating precision is exploited and discussed. Even though archaeomagnetic dating is now well established in Italy, more high-quality archaeomagnetic data are still necessary to extend the SV curves back in time and to refine the short-term behaviour of the geomagnetic field's variation. In particular, the improvement of the intensity SV curve and the refinement of short-term and abrupt intensity variations can open new horizons on the establishment of archaeomagnetism as a potential dating tool for displaced archaeological artifacts, too.

SESSION 3

OUTCOMES FROM TRAINING SCHOOLS & OTHER TOOLS

Chair: Ekhine Garcia-Garcia

17. SCIENCE COLLABORATION WITHOUT BORDERS: INTRODUCING LARGE-SCALE GPR INVESTIGATIONS IN FINLAND

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In March of 2020, researchers from the University of Helsinki and NTNU conducted a multichannel GPR survey at lake Lepinjärvi, Karjaa, SW Finland, as a SAGA-supported Short Term Scientific Mission (STSM). The Lepinjärvi region is a known hotspot of prehistoric human activity and habitation, with multitudes of previously identified burial and settlement

sites, especially from the Iron Age, sprinkled around the lakeshore. During the four days of scanning, three areas totalling 5 ha were measured, making it the largest and the highest resolution archaeological GPR study carried out in Finland to date.

Due to COVID, the post-processing and interpretation of the data were done in an online workshop supported by the SAGA Virtual Mobility Grant. Even though the surveyed area has a complex geological background as a result of the region's successive glacial, marine and lacustrine past, several possible non-modern man-made features could be identified.

A small number of these were test pitted in August 2022 with interesting results: for example, in some cases, we were able to pick out the 5–10 cm bottom slivers of pit features that are left after hundreds of years of ploughing, one of which was C14 dated to c. 300 CE. Considering especially the small number of Iron Age settlement sites known and excavated in Finland, a compelling argument can be made for wider adoption of this method.

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18. THE 4TH SAGA TRAINING SCHOOL 'ER AND GPR SURVEY AND RELATED GEOARCHAEOLOGICAL METHODS'

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Geophysics as a field of study is relatively new in North Macedonia. The training school, which was organised in Valandovo in April 2022 is one of the pioneer steps towards its development. The overall idea was to help a fledgling dedicated state geophysics team (part of the Archaeological Museum of the R. N. Macedonia) develop in an under-resourced and under-researched part of the southern Balkans. A core team, with additional field personnel on individual projects, needed to develop the necessary skills to plan, undertake, process and interpret their own surveys. The team owns a Mala GPR system, for which TigerGeo has already provided pro-bono field, processing and interpretative training. These earlier works needed building upon, with detailed training in electrical methods and soil physics to suit the location and typical sites. In addition, the participants were trained in electrical and GPR fieldwork skills so they can be able to support the core team.

Central to the ideology of the training was to use real sites that are undergoing current research because this immediately maximizes the benefit to the local organizers and the wider community. It allowed teaching to be integrated with real-life questions and prob-

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lems which enhanced the experience of the students. In this particular case, by integrating the training within established archaeological research objectives, the work also demonstrates the wider benefits of geophysical work in an area where little has been done. By doing this, a case is made directly for better future resourcing of the national geophysical team.

The hands-on training happened at two archaeological sites in Valandovo's region. The location and the abundance of natural resources made this region a really attractive location through the centuries, and it has a continuity of occupation from the Iron Age until today. The sites are located in the vicinity of the city and are from different periods. One of them is Stakina Češma, a Late Roman luxurious villa (3rd – 4th century AD), and the other one, Isar Marvinci is an Early Antique city with a massive necropolis with graves from the 8th century BC until 4th century AD.

Acknowledgments

This training school was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu) and the NI Archaeological Museum of the Republic of North Macedonia. Special thanks to the trainers from TigerGeo Ltd and Liverpool's John Moores University, UK.

19. THE 3RD SAGA TRAINING SCHOOL 'MAGNETIC LABORATORY METHODS IN SUPPORT OF ARCHAEOLOGY

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The training school was held in Prague, Czech Republic, from 28th March until 31st March 2022 and hosted by the Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Science and co-institutional support of the Institute of Geology of the CAS, the laboratory of Paleomagnetism. The lecturers were high recognised specialists in palaeomagnetism, archaeomagnetism, environmental magnetism, geoarchaeology; Elina Aidona from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Geology, Geophysical Department (Greece); Neli Jordanova from the National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences); Simo Spassov from the Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium; Eduard Petrovský from the Institute of Geophysics (Czech Academy of Sciences); Hana Grison (Local Organiser) from the Institute of Geophysics (Czech Academy of Sciences); and Petr Schnabl from the Paleomagnetic laboratory in Pruhonice, the Institute of Geology (Czech Academy of Sciences)

The training school aim was to improve participant's ability to obtain, analyse and interpret magnetic data with relevance to archaeo-geophysical research methods. Magnetic property characterisation focused on soil and archaeological material (magnetic susceptibility, remanence and hysteresis characterization etc.). Data analysis and interpretation session showed a variety of soils from 'natural' to archaeological ones. The applications

of Archaeomagnetic dating techniques was introduced with reference to archaeology case studies. Hands-on sessions demonstrated how to perform archaeomagnetic measurements, incl. sampling, data processing.

To enhanced understanding of a variety of magnetic data, participants gained a broader understanding of the importance of magnetic analyses related to a range of archaeological applications e.g. effect of geomagnetic field, stagnant water, past settlement, etc. They got a broader knowledge of application of a mineral magnetic approach to determine paleo-firing temperatures. During hands-on sessions the participants broadened their knowledge of how to collect oriented samples and how to perform in-situ/in laboratory measurements with a variety of instruments.

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MODELLING, DATA ANALYSIS AND INTEGRATION

Chair: Isabelle LECOMTE

20. KNOW YOUR ENEMY: PARAMETERISING THE DESCRIPTION OF NOISE IN GEOPHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS FOR ARCHAEOLOGY

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Prior to the interpretation of archaeological geophysical survey results it is beneficial to minimise unwanted data ('noise'). To decide what processing can be applied, such noise has to be characterised quantitatively first. This contribution describes some parameters that can be used.

Geophysical measurements contain the sought after 'signals' and a 'background' against

which the signals stand out as anomalies. Both components may be affected by noise. The latter can hence be considered a third component of the geophysical measurements. It may be (i) internal, related to the instrumentation, (ii) caused by variations in the use of the instruments (e.g. while walking with a magnetometer), (iii) created by external signals entering the measurements (e.g. magnetic storms), or (iv) produced by the ground's spatial variability, usually referred to as 'soil noise' (Schmidt, et al., 2020). Once noise forms part of the measurement data it can be very difficult to remove. Therefore, all avoidable sources (e.g. (ii) – poor use of instruments) should be eliminated during survey planning and execution.

To select processing methods and parameters that help minimising noise, or to recognise and ignore it during interpretation, requires its characterisation. Some authors categorised unwanted data components as 'errors' that can be corrected and 'noise' that is unpredictable (Ghezzi, et al., 2019). Others preferred to base their discussion on the spatial appearance distinguishing between correlated and uncorrelated noise (Graham & Scollar, 1976). For the current discussion we consider all unwanted signals to be noise and focus on four particular forms: (a) random noise, (b) spatial noise, (c) non-stationary noise and (d) sampling noise.

Geostatistics is based on models of spatial data variation ('variograms') that can also be used to examine the similarity of neighbouring measurements which is related to the level of random noise. For this study, such variograms were calculated for fluxgate gradiometer data from two sites (Figure 1). The negligible nugget effect (vertical intercept) and a range value of 0.8 m and 1.4 m (level of correlation) for sites A and B, respectively demonstrate the minimal contribution of random instrument noise to the data and that measurements are consistent over the typical size of small scale anomalies. A different approach to the analysis of noise uses the calculation of spatial frequencies (Figure 2). Given sufficiently high sampling rates small-scale variations generated by spatial noise can be seen as spikes of high wave-numbers and removed with a suitable low-pass filter, which is not possible if the data are under-sampled.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu).

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Site A

Site B

Figure 1: Variograms calculated along the horizontal x- axis for data from two sites.

Site A

Site B

Figure 2: Spatial frequencies calculated along the horizontal x- axis for data from two sites.

21.1D/3D SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF LOW FREQUENCY ELECTRO-MAGNETIC METHOD IN ARCHAEOLOGY FOR SOILS AND FEATURES CHARACTERIZATION: REVIEW AND PROGRESS

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Compared to other geophysical methods, frequency domain electromagnetic (FDEM) surveying is not widely used. There are several reasons that underly this reality. First, there are specific technical constraints that impede straightforward use of these devices (offset, calibration), alongside the need for stable data acquisition systems which minimize the influence of roll and pitch on obtained measurements. However, EM methods offer the possibility to investigate complex electrical and magnetic properties at different depths of investigation, and at different operating frequencies.

Through the characterization of the spatial distribution of electrical and magnetic properties, it is possible to go beyond a simple mapping of apparent geophysical properties. Inversion algorithms make it possible to proceed to a 3D or pseudo-3D characterization of the mapped features and soils distribution. As a consequence of its potential, FDEM allows investigating the link between soil properties, their spatial distribution and their physical characteristics. This integral interpretative potential makes it highly valuable as part of geo-archaeological studies.

However, these possibilities require a good knowledge of the sensitivities of this type of device to the different geophysical properties and geometry of the mapped features. For many years now, their sensitivity to 1D approaches has been known, whether for electrical conductivity or magnetic susceptibility.

We discuss here the computations of 3D sensitivities for different devices and different configurations in order to complete the first results from the 1970s and which may explain some difficulties encountered in the characterisation of buried features. We will focus in particular on magnetic susceptibility, which seems to us to be a particularly interesting proxy for anthropic activities and which must be well mastered for cross-applications with the magnetic method for example.

Acknowledgments

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In phase signal at 5000 Hz in HCP (GEM2) configuration for 1.66 meter coils spacing at $z = 0.06$ m

In phase signal at 5000 Hz in HCP (GEM2) configuration for 1.66 meter coils spacing at $x = 0.1$ m

Figure 1: 3D magnetic susceptibility sensitivity for the GEM2 at 5 kHz.

In phase signal at 5000 Hz in HCP (DualEM) configuration for 1.0 meter coils spacing at $z = 0.06$ m

In phase signal at 5000 Hz in HCP (DualEM) configuration for 1.0 meter coils spacing at $x = 0.1$ m

Figure 2: 3D magnetic susceptibility sensitivity for the DualEM in HCP configuration and 1 meter coil spacing.

22. DEPTH DETERMINATION OF POTENTIAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL STRUCTURES ON TOTAL MAGNETIC ANOMALY MAPS: OLUZ MOUND EXAMPLE

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Determining the subsurface structures in the archaeological excavation area before excavation and non-destructively is of great importance in reducing the cost and preventing the loss of time and labor. This study, the depth calculation part of the quantitative analysis of total magnetic anomaly maps on archaeological sites, aims to analyze the depth values of potential buried structures that cause anomalies from an archaeological excavation area's total magnetic anomaly maps.

Initially, a synthetic model containing five blocks was formed, and its boundaries were

determined on the developed total magnetic anomaly map. The depth values of the mentioned structures were analyzed at the points corresponding to these building boundaries (Figure 1a-b).

Depth values of blocks were calculated by using Tilt Angle Depth (TAD), Source Parameter Imaging (SPI), and Improved Source Parameter Imaging (iSPI) methods. The depth values calculated by all three methods were compared and interpreted. Furthermore, as a field application, the depth values at the potential structure boundaries were calculated on the total magnetic anomaly map of the Oluz - mound area (Figure 2a-b). Consequently, the depth values are visualized on the simplified structure map of the region by combining the potential structure boundary locations.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank Davut Aydoğan and Fethi Ahmet Yüksel for their support.

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Figure 1: (a) 3D geometric position of the model consisting of 5 prismatic blocks, (b) Reduction to pole map with model blocks and calculation profiles (Toktay, 2022).

Figure 2: (a) Amasya Oluz Mound total magnetic anomaly map (reduced to pole), Tilt Angle map, and depth calculation profiles, (b) Map showing simplified horizontal locations and vertical depths of the potential structural complex of the study area (Toktay,2022).

23. MODELLING ARCHAEOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT AND GEOPHYSICAL RESPONSE USING CESIUM MAGNETOMETRY IN ROMAN ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE ARGAMUM

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Argamum-(Orgame) is one of the four oldest Greek settlements in the Black Sea. Founded around the middle of the VIIIth BC on the northern coast of Dobrudja-Romania, the city occupies the end of Cape Dolojman which dominates an important lagoon complex located south of the Danube delta. The main purpose of the geophysical prospections of the spring of 2022, when a cesium vapor magnetometer (G864) was used, was to identify the fortification elements in the main gate zone specific to this type of settlement and to establish a new archaeological research strategy. The delimitation area for the magnetometric scanning was made in accord to the presence of ceramic material on the surface, subsequently, assign-ing, using a GPS system TRIMBLE R4, two grids aligned in a north-south direction, inside de fortress near the main gate and traced respecting the geomorpho-

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logical configuration and vegetation present on the site. The data was bidirectionally collected from a grid with a distance between the lines measuring 1 m, with 25 readings per meter. Cesium magnetometer surveys were conducted to identify fortification walls and adjacent buried structures. This paper presents the interpretation of the large magnetic anomalies observed on the two investigated grids, typical for a fortification wall (Figure 1).

Archaeological research from the summer of 2022 has confirmed the results obtained using the geomagnetic prospection method and were confirm the existence of the fortification wall and adjacent buildings in the main gate zone. In the second step, we used the Potent Q software for using the modeling process relating to the dimensions, position, forms, and inclination of the buried artifacts (Figure 2). Finally, the Main Gate area -Argamum fortress study demonstrated that magnetometry is capable of providing a rapid overview of the distribution of buried artifacts which may prove useful to excavation design efforts. The increased availability of cesium magnetometric investigations provides the possibility to extend the investigation of individual archaeological sites into a much wider archaeological context, maximizing the information that can be recovered in a relatively short period of field work.

Acknowledgments

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Figure 1: Magnetic field anomaly map – left side perimeter.

Figure 2: Modelling process for section B-B.

24. SEARCHING FOR INNOVATIVE WAYS OF DATA ANALYSIS IN ARCHAEOLOGICAL PROSPECTION

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The presentation focuses on brief characterisation of activities of SAGA Working Group 3. In searching for innovative ways of data analysis, we finally focused on three branches: the topic of different data types, the topic of the integration (done on geophysical and geochemical data) and geophysical data as compositional data.

The topic of different data types was done due to the needs of the integration topic: we need to know, what we are working with and what we can do with the data, as we tried to move the integration beyond usual comparative approach to the approach where the data are mathematically changed. Therefore, this activity was focused on characterization of the data types: what is their positive/negative aspect – can they be both like e.g. magnetometer data? Or is it possible for them to contain zero as a value? Are there some data, where only positive values make sense (like geochemical elemental content)? This influences what we can do mathematically and what makes sense (e.g. computing average of magnetometer data can be done, but it hardly brings results of sense).

The integration was focused on finding the methodical workflow / algorithm for the integration of the geophysical data and geochemical data. We developed the workflow on the testing datasets from the Czech site of Bělčice (magnetometer and XRF data). The workflow contains several main steps and many substeps. The steps are designed so they can be applied also separately without the need to follow the whole workflow. The main

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steps are: randomization (used for estimation of signal / noise in the geophysical data), linear models (between geophysical and geochemical data), and the integration, which contains several substeps (prediction of geochemical data based on linear model, computed as weighted average between the interpolated and predicted geochemistry and several ways how to perform PCA on the results). This task produced not only the workflow, but also the whole datasets and all the computational scripts will be available freely to anybody on Zenodo repository (after the publication).

The last topic was searching for answer, if the geophysical data can be viewed as compositional data (similarly to geochemical data). We have prepared the paper where we discuss and formulate that GPR data can be seen this way.

All three topics are prepared as papers to be published and are now in various stages of review process.

Acknowledgments

These activities were also supported by the workings of some of our colleagues who contributed to the papers prepared from these activities; namely they are: Mercedes Solla, Ekhine Garcia-Garcia, François-Xavier Simon, Nikos Papadopoulos, Roman Křivánek and Alžběta Danielisová.

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It was also supported by project INTER-COST (LTC19) subprogram of program INTEREXCELLENCE by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic, Project: 'Geochemical insight into non-destructive archaeological research"; project number: LTC19016.

25. NEW STATISTICAL APPROACHES TO THE INTEGRATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY DATA

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Kristiansen (2014) envisaged a "third science revolution" in archaeology, characterized by so-called "Big Data", new quantitative and modelling approaches, and novel theoretical approaches that link these advances in data and methods. These tendencies in archaeology, now well-established, mirror developments in other scientific fields, for example in geography and allied environmental sciences, where new statistical methods (or old statistical methods applied in new ways) are increasingly used to explore large, sometimes messy datasets and shed light on problems previously considered intractable. Examples

include the application of agent-based models for understanding human-environment interaction cycles in ancient landscapes (Boogers and Daems 2022), the incorporation of spatial interactions to improve understanding of urban scaling laws (Altmann 2020), and the growth of interest in simulation-based approaches, e.g. to generate multiple random “replicates” of spatial patterns of sites and artefacts (Hewitt et al 2020).

Randomization-based approaches are also potentially of interest in archaeological prospection, as a means of separating noise from data and for integrating data from different survey techniques. This provided the motivation for a Short-Term Scientific mission (STSM) at the Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague in September 2021. During the STSM, the authors worked productively at the intersection of their different interests and backgrounds on the integration of geophysical and geochemical data in the R environment.

Key outcomes from this collaboration included the development of a new methodological approach to integration referred to as “deep integration” to help differentiate it from simple comparison methods, and a set of R-based statistical tools to enable the approach to be applied to other case study sites and datasets. The new approach, which was the subject of a scientific publication (Horák et al under review) involved determining the degree to which geophysical data differed from random, the application of linear models to find relationships between geophysical and geochemical data, and the integration of both datasets to produce a single output with new characteristics.

Exploratory application of the new approach to the integration of geophysical and geochemical datasets from the Iron Age site of Bělčice in Bohemia, Czechia, revealed patterns not present in either of the original datasets, highlighting the potential for future application in the understanding of spatial distribution of occupation at archaeological sites.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action SAGA: The Soil Science & Archaeo-Geophysics Alliance - CA17131 (www.saga-cost.eu), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu).

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SESSION 5

INTEGRATED PROXY STUDIES FOR SITE PRESERVATION, MONITORING AND EVALUATING RISK FOR NATURAL DISASTERS / CLIMATE CHANGE

Chair: Clare WILSON

26. THE CHERISH TOOLKIT: APPLYING EARTH SCIENCES TO MON- ITOR AND UNDERSTAND THE IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE CULTURAL HERITAGE OF OUR SEAS AND COASTS

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The CHERISH climate change and coastal heritage project began in January 2017. Phase 1 of the project, which ran until June 2022, involved the survey and investigation of some of the most iconic coastal locations in Ireland and Wales.

A variety of scientific methods were employed by the CHERISH team to monitor and understand the past, present and near-future impacts of climate change on the rich cultural heritage of our seas and coasts. This paper summarises the findings within the CHERISH Good Practice Guide which shares our experiences and practices by detailing the CHERISH 'toolkit' – the technologies and methods we employed. The guidelines focus on individual methods within our 'toolkit', and provide overview, analysis, and evaluation across a standardised set of criteria covering aspects such as applicable environments, scale of coverage, resolution and accuracy, cost and outputs.

For each toolkit approach a case study showcases how the method was employed at a CHERISH study site. The CHERISH 'toolkit' represents an integrated and multidisciplinary approach; the individual methods were rarely used in isolation. We have therefore drawn together the analysis of individual methods as a visual overview for comparison to help guide users and decision making.

Here, we also examine which are best employed to monitor weather and climate change impacts in the coast zone. In addition we showcase the integrated approach with our final set of case studies bringing the 'toolkit' together using the example of two study sites, Dinas Dinlle coastal hillfort in Wales and Ferriter's promontory fort in Ireland.

Acknowledgments

The project is funded through the Ireland-Wales Programme 2014-2020, part of the European Regional Development Fund, which focusses on seeking solutions to shared challenges on both sides of the Irish Sea. The Ireland-Wales 2014-2020 Programme is governed by the Welsh European Funding Office (WEFO). The project is also supported through the Heritage Council in Ireland.

Figure 1: CHERISH toolkit graphic illustrating the integrated and multidisciplinary approach to survey on land and under the sea. Key; 1. Lidar, 2. UAV survey, 3. Satellite imagery, 4. Aerial survey, 5. Geophysical survey, 6. Coring, 7. GNSS survey, 8. Erosion monitoring, 9. Terrestrial laser scanning, 10. Excavation, sampling & dating, 11. Marine mapping, 12. Underwater archaeological survey

27. THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATED GEOPHYSICS IN THE DETERMINATION OF IMPORTANTLY DEFORMED SUBSURFACE ARCHAEOLOGICAL STRUCTURES

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Ground slipping and subsidence after some events such as earthquakes, landslides and tsunamis in archaeological sites cause significant vertical and horizontal displacements in the archaeological context. It is known that archaeological sites in the regions such as the Levant, Anatolia, Aegean and Iran, which are under the influence of young tectonics due to Alpine Orogeny, are generally affected by important geological phenomena that occur based on earthquakes.

In the geophysical studies applied in such areas, it becomes difficult to make a geophysical interpretation as a result of the mixing of the archaeological context due to such events and the development of horizontal-vertical deformations in the ground (Figure 1).

For this reason, geophysical studies in such areas must be applied in an integrated manner (at least 3 methods; magnetic, electrical resistivity tomography and GPR) and thus it will be possible to obtain more interpretive geophysical results in the determination of buried archaeological features in the subsurface.

In this study, the results of integrated geophysical studies conducted in archaeological sites occurred with significant earthquake deformations such as Sardis, Şapinuwa and Hattuša and their contribution to geophysical interpretation are discussed. In Figure 2, the results of the integrated geophysical studies carried out in Area H in Şapinuwa and the drawings and photographs of the structure obtained during the excavations in the area are given. As can be seen from the figure, magnetic gradiometer and ERT methods yielded a result in full agreement with the excavation results of the buried archaeological structure. However, since the GPR method is greatly affected by the horizontal and vertical deformations due to earthquakes, it did not show a sufficiently successful result in terms of depth slice. In such cases, comparing the radargram analysis of the GPR study with other methods provides a more successful interpretation.

As a result, in order to improve the interpretation in such areas, besides using multiple methodologies, some improvements should be made during the process stage of the methods.

Figure 1: Archaeological structures that have been highly deformed as a result of the earthquake. (a) and (b) Sardis Field-55, (c) Šapinuwa, (d) Hattuša.

Figure 2: The results of the integrated geophysical studies in an area exposed to earthquake deformation in Šapinuwa and the drawing and photographs of archaeological structure after excavation. (a) drawing, (b) magnetic gradiometer, (c) GPR (d=0-1.1 m), (d) ERT (d=0-1.2m), (e) photographs after excavation.

28. PROSPECTING FLOODED STONE AGE SITES. MULTIVARIATE GEOPHYSICAL PROXIES FROM A HYDROELECTRIC DAM

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Hydroelectric dams represent a transformed mountain landscape, more or less unexplored by means of geophysical methods. In Norway, dams constructed earlier than 1960 – with sites and features never surveyed nor excavated prior to construction – are subject to a sector fee in order to allow and finance intensive archaeological investigations whenever water levels are low. One of these dams is the Aursjøen watercourse, situated in the mountains in between Eastern, Western and Central Norway. In 2006, a pilot project revealed its great archaeological potential, and the main purpose of the current project is to study cultural encounters in a long-time perspective – from the Ice Age to historical periods. In addition, the project will be aiming at developing new strategies and methods for investigating such transformed sites, having been periodically flooded through more than half a century. The Aursjøen project started in 2022 and will be running until 2026/2027. In this paper I will present the preliminary results from an Early Neolithic site, investigated by a range of geophysical methods in the first year of the project. Including both magnetic susceptibility, gradiometer and ground penetrating radar, the possibilities and limitations of each of these methods will be discussed, as well as the combination itself. The preliminary conclusion, however, is that geophysical methods do have a great potential, both in locating and delimiting sites and features, prioritizing excavation grids, and understanding the wider landscape context.

Acknowledgments

The prospection is part of large-scale development-led excavation project, a collaboration between the KHM University Museum, NTNU University Museum, Innlandet County Council, Møre & Romsdal County Council, and the Sami Parliament, financed by the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy through sector fees.

29. UNDERSTANDING THE CITYSCAPE OF SOBA BY MEANS OF MAGNETOMETRY AND GROUND-PENETRATING RADAR DATA

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Soba, the capital of Alwa, was one of the largest African cities during the Middle Ages. The remains of Soba (estimated 275 ha of the archaeological site) are located in the eastern suburbs of Khartoum, on the right bank of the Blue Nile, about 20 kilometers upstream from the confluence with the White Nile (Drzewiecki et al. 2022). Excavations carried out during the 20th century revealed remains of monumental architecture dating from around the

6th to 14th century (Welsby 1991, Welsby and Daniels 1998). Nowadays, the rapid development of Khartoum means Soba is one of the most threatened archaeological sites in Sudan (Figure 1). To characterise the archaeological remains and to obtain information about the spatial organization of the city, a strategy that utilizes large-scale geophysical research was developed. A combination of fluxgate magnetometry and Ground-Penetrating Radar was applied, supported by detailed orthomosaics and DTMs, archival maps, and satellite imaging, integrated into a GIS database (Ryndziewicz et al. 2021). A significant challenge met during the research was the specific geomorphology of the lower reaches of the Blue Nile floodplain. This tributary accounts for as much as $60\pm 4\%$ transportation of the suspended sediment in the annual flow regime of the Nile (Woodward et al. 2022). Fine-grained sediments from the Blue Nile Basin, derived from volcanic rocks from the Ethiopian Highlands, are characterized by high magnetic susceptibility and cause strong electromagnetic wave attenuation, hindering the operation of GPR. The survey covering about 46.5 ha (magnetometry) supplemented with GPR data (about 7.5 ha) provided a detailed map of the geophysical response of subsurface structures.

Based on the research results, it is possible to locate several clusters of dense buildings spread over a large area. In numerous cases, individual buildings, some of a monumental character, can be identified (Figure 2). As long as the exact dating of individual structures is unknown, it is difficult to draw precise conclusions about the phases and directions of Soba's spatial development. Archaeological data indicate, however, that initially Soba had a polycentric character known from other African cities from the Middle Age period (Drzewiecki and Michalik 2021). Later, around the 9th century, the administrative and religious center within mound B became the dominant component of the urban landscape. This model does not fit into the city-forming patterns known from European and Middle Eastern cities thus the geophysical data seems crucial to understand Soba's cityscape.

Acknowledgments

The research in Soba is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (Grant Number UMO-2018/29/B/HS3/02533) directed by Dr. Mariusz Drzewiecki (Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology, University of Warsaw).

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Figure 1: Location of the study area. Recent decades of intensive infrastructure development meant that out of the 275 hectares of the site, only about 50 ha remained available for geophysical research. Background map: Google Earth.

Figure 2: Example of the data (area OS): magnetometry (left) and GPR (right). Background map by Mariusz Drzewiecki (PCMA UW).

SESSION 6

UPCOMING PROJECTS

Chair: Jörg FASSBINDER

30. IN SEARCH FOR THE ANSWERS — GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH ON THE WWII EXTERMINATION CAMPS AREAS AND EXCAVATION STRATEGIES AT MEMORIAL SITES

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For many years, a research team at the Faculty of Geodesy and Cartography (Warsaw University of Technology) has been looking for traces of the functioning of the extermination camps from World War II located in Poland. Last year our team started two projects dedicated to the Treblinka II and Kulmhof-on-Ner extermination camps and the Riese labor camp system associated with KL Auschwitz-Birkenau concentration and KL Gross Rosen camps. Both projects aim to determine the structure and arrange essential historical facilities within the studied camps and indicate the location of labor camps, respectively. For both projects, a vital element of the methodology is the combination of spatial data with geophysical research, with particular emphasis on GPR, magnetic, and geoelectric methods. The planned tasks as part of these projects are entered in the COST Action SAGA program, i.e., research activities combining archaeo-geophysics, soil science, and geology. The planned presentation will present the current research state and propose new cooperation opportunities for the coming years.

Acknowledgments

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31. INVESTIGATING THE MIGRATION PERIOD RINGFORTS ON ÖLAND, SWEDEN WITH GPR

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Öland, an island in the Baltic Sea on the east coast of Sweden, is a unique archaeological site because of the numerous remains of stone fences, house foundations and graves from the Roman Iron Age and the Migration Period. The most striking stone features are the ca. 20 ringforts, defined as massive oval limestone walls enclosing dense radial stone house foundations built between 200-700 BCE (Stenberger 1933, Fallgren 2006, 2008). These types of stone structures are easy to detect with ground-penetrating radar (GPR) and magnetometer surveys.

Currently, the only fully archaeologically excavated ringfort is Eketorp, excavated by Märten Stenberger 1964-1973. The excavation revealed dense house foundations inside the limestone walls, similar to the foundations visible at Ismantorp ringfort. Successful geophysical surveys have been carried out in the ringforts before. In Sandby borg, Bårby borg and Sörby borg, geophysical surveys have detected traces of radial house foundations (Viberg et al. 2014, Viberg et al. 2020) similar to the ones in Eketorp.

The project Climate, Conflict and Crisis - Societal Change in Middle Iron Age Scandinavia by the Archaeological Research Laboratory at Stockholm University will commence in 2023. It will aim to investigate the Ölandic ringforts from the Migration Period with a wide span of different research methods. As part of the project, we will continue to investigate the Ölandic ringforts with GPR. The geophysical survey will utilize a 500 MHz multichannel antenna GPR system provided by Malå Geoscience. The plan is to document the ringforts' internal layout, such as possible house foundations and openings, and the landscape around them, like water supplies and defence systems. By revealing the ringforts' internal structures, we hope to further understand the purpose and use of the ringforts and make a complete internal mapping of the ringforts that can be used for further research and excavations.

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32. UNCOVERING THE SECRETS OF THE TUMULUS OF LAONA IN PALAEPAPHOS, CYPRUS, THROUGH AN INTEGRATED GEOPHYSICAL APPROACH

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The Palaepaphos Urban Landscape Project (PULP) was initiated in 2006, following an extensive geophysical prospection of the wider area of Kouklia-Palaepaphos in 2003. Since 2012 the project has been investigating a unique in Cyprus man-made mound on Laona (Gkouma et al. 2021), which is clearly visible to the east of the sanctuary of the Cypriot Aphrodite (Karageorghis 2005).

Excavations revealed that the mound covers an earlier monumental rampart of the early 5th c. BC, which has so far been uncovered for circa 160 m. from under the east and north slopes of the tumulus. A small (4x4m) stone-built structure completely filled with marl has also been located close to the center of the tumulus.

In order to investigate the unexcavated NW part of the tumulus, geophysical techniques were used to reach its deeper strata. The purpose of the 2022 geophysical project was to map the vertical and horizontal variation of the subsurface resistivity of the tumulus up to a depth of about 10 meters below the elevated surface for possible architectural features. The GPR was employed mainly along the fringes of the lower slopes of the tumulus to the east and close to the limits of the tumulus to the north and west. A total area of 2,600 square meters was covered with the Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) and 1,780 square meters were scanned through the ground penetrating radar (GPR).

The ERT interpretation was based on the integration of the results from the 2D vertical sections and the horizontal slices produced respectively by the 2D and 3D inversion of the tomographic data. The combination of all the 2D resistivity section resulted in a simplified

geological section showing a vertical stratigraphy consisting of a marl layer at the base, a conglomerate formation above it and a clayish material of about ~2,450 m³ that was used to cover the summit of the tumulus (max. h. 114m asl) (Figure 1). The GPR interpretation followed a specific pipeline producing 2D slices with increasing depth (Sarris 2020). Horizontal and vertical slices and 3D volumetric representations were produced for both ERT and GPR measurements suggesting sections of surrounding and internal walls along with a number of internal targets that are related to discontinuities of the conglomerate bedrock. Towards the east, the GPR shallow reflectors indicated an excellent correspondence to the magnetic measurements obtained during an earlier (2003) geophysical campaign (Figure 2).

Excavations are under way to uncover the secrets of the rest of the tumulus.

Acknowledgments

The INSIGHT 2022-2024 project is funded by the Leventis Research Programmes of the University of Cyprus.

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Figure 1. 3D view of ERT 2D sections. The grey surface is the top surface of the conglomerate. The low resistivity area (blue color) is the clayish filling material of the tumulus.

Figure 2. The most indicative GPR depth slices, in which the potential geophysical features are indicated. Intense reflectors are shown around the fringes of the tumulus.

33. INTRODUCING SENSING IBERIANSCAPES – EXPLORATION OF INDIGENOUS SETTLEMENTS FROM THE IRON AGE ON THE EASTERN COAST OF THE IBERIAN PENINSULA USING MINIMAL INVASIVE STRATEGIES

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SENSING IBERIANSCAPES is a 4-year project to start in August 2023. The goal is to investigate indigenous protohistoric Iberian communities in the western Mediterranean and the interaction with their environs, using minimal invasive strategies. It follows a test survey carried out in 2013 (Cuenca-García 2014) and a larger study (GEOIbers, AICO2020/250) that revealed the potential of geophysical prospection methods to extensively detect features related to Iberian fortified settlements (or oppida), metalworking production sites and necropoli.

This project brings a multi-scalar approach to explore urban, production and burial sites from a macro (landscape) down to a micro (feature) perspective. By using a combination of remote and proximal sensing methods (including ground-based geophysical surveys) surface and subsurface archaeological and paleoenvironmental features will be spatially identified, mapped, and characterised. Targeted trench excavation or coring/augering will follow to validate critical findings of the sensed data and to obtain samples for further analyses of some key features to add to the final interpretation.

Our expectation is that, apart from the new insights at a site/feature-level on protohistoric urbanistic layout and characteristics of structures within and beyond the oppidum, the study will provide new information at the rather unexplored landscape level. For example, identifying and connecting existing or new sites or other archaeological or paleo-environmental elements of interest. The integration of soil sampling for targeted feature-level characterisation will bring data validation and an extra dimension in the interpretation of the sensed datasets.

We will work to contribute to expand the knowledge about the dynamics that the Iberian groups established with their environment to organise their communities (urbanism), exploit resources (especially those related to the tradition, highly specialized but little known, in iron forging), and whose remains rest in intriguing specific locations (necropolis). The research results will be transferred to stakeholders working on the digital musealisation of such assets.

Acknowledgments

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SESSION 7

OTHER CASE STUDIES & PROJECT IDEAS

Chair: Arne Anderson Stamnes

34. PALAEOCHANNELS OF THE RAKHIGARHI HINTERLAND IN HARYANA, INDIA

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Despite the tendency to associate Indus-civilization settlements with palaeochannels, landscape surveys have demonstrated that the location of Rakhigarhi, which is the largest Indus settlement, and several other settlements in its hinterland do not correlate with palaeochannel courses (Singh et al., 2010). Several Indus settlements in the Rakhigarhi hinterland are aligned in a linear pattern, which suggests the distribution of settlements along a watercourse which may have diverged and intersected at certain points (Singh et al., 2010). Notably, the ancient settlement mound of Rakhigarhi is surrounded by large-size ponds (Singh et al., 2010). If these are the remnants of an abandoned waterway and if they were connected to the Chautang palaeochannel, which originated in the Himalayas, remains to be investigated. Moreover, the Himalayan source which drained into the Chautang has not been attested through isotopic studies (Dave et al., 2019). As shown by previous research, climatic shifts had temporally and spatially variable impacts over the Indus zone (Dixit et al., 2014; Petrie et al., 2017). Therefore, exploring long-term dynamics

in hydrology in relation to local variations in hydroclimatic regimes is essential in order to assess the ecological changes within the Rakhigarhi hinterland.

The proposed study aims to reconstruct the sources and the hydrology of palaeochannels in the Rakhigarhi hinterland, and the evolution of large-sized ponds that surround the ancient settlement. It will use particle-size analysis, multi-collector inductively-coupled plasma mass-spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS), thermal ionization mass spectrometry (TIMS), optically-stimulated luminescence, and micromorphology. The results of the study will expand the knowledge regarding the evolution of regional hydrology in relation to the development of the urban landscape and the hinterland of Rakhigarhi.

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35. USING GPR METHOD FOR ARCHEOLOGICAL PROSPECTION A CASE STUDY IN KOSTURINO, NORTH MACEDONIA

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Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) is a non-destructive geophysical method that is based on the analysis of the electromagnetic waves, and in the recent years it's one of the most applied methods for detecting of the potential buried archaeological features, having a very significant role in collecting the necessary data for mapping them.

In this abstract partly are presented the results from the preliminary GPR measurements performed at an archaeological site of a Neolithic settlement, situated near the village of Kosturino, Strumica, which according to the discovered remains has been considered to be approximately 7000 years old. The GPR measurements were performed along the grid of 49 longitudinal and transverse profiles, using an antenna with central frequency of 300 MHz (GCB300, Geoscanners, Sweden). The main purpose of the measurements was the

preliminary mapping of potential underground archaeo-logical objects before the beginning of the archaeological excavation activities.

Data processing was performed in 2 phases. In the first phase, processing of the raw data was performed. The 2D processed radargrams, based on the amplitudes of the reflected electromagnetic waves indicate the position and depth of the potential buried archaeological objects, but for this type of research, interpolation of the radargrams and 3D display is necessary for more detailed mapping and interpretation.

The second phase of the data analysis consisted of post-processing, i.e integration and interpolation of the 2D processed radargrams and generation of a 3D GPR model. The final mapping of the potential underground objects was performed based on the generated 3D GPR cube and 2D GPR time-slices at different estimated depths.

36. MAGNETOMETRIC SURVEY DATA AND THEIR TESTING BY ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXCAVATIONS IN POIENESTI-LUCASEUCA CULTURE SETTLEMENTS: PRELIMINARY RESULTS

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Our focus will be on the study of the complex phenomena that defined the last centuries of the pre-Christian era in South-Eastern European territories. It is becoming increasingly clear that the complexity and objectivity of the projected panorama remain limited due to their reception mainly through the prism of funerary sites. Massive accumulations of information on the living spaces of the populations of this period is needed to balance the situation. The use of traditional methods (which have so far been used almost without exception for Second Iron Age sites in these areas) are usually time-consuming, laborious and expensive.

In order to maximize the efficiency of such investigations, we have proposed to diversify the methods of acquiring such information through preventive prospecting, trying to balance the share of invasive and non-invasive investigations. Beyond the preparatory character of the surveys, we aimed to open the perspective of collecting useful information for the maximum possible understanding of the site, even without using invasive investigations, i.e. to develop a model for the study of similar sites by these methods. One of the activities aimed at carrying out magnetometer surveys in the Ivancea settlement of the Poienesti-Lucaseuca culture (Republic of Moldova), with subsequent verification of each type of anomaly by traditional methods. At first, in collaboration with colleagues from the University of Iasi, only a small peripheral area of the site was scanned, which was later extended to 4 ha. Respectively, a series of punctual archaeological excavations were carried out in the various types of anomalies with the aim of delimiting its functionalities. Later, in collaboration with colleagues from Eastern Atlas (Germany), in the framework of a DFG project,

SESSION 7

the area covered by magnetometer surveys was extended to 12 ha.

The new image, correlated with an orderly surface survey, has made it possible to delimit several spatial-chronological horizons and in particular to delimit the boundaries of the Second Iron Age settlement. The processing of the images obtained provided the possibility of delimiting certain types of archaeological features (Figure 1), which were subsequently verified by archaeological excavations (Figure 2). Importantly, some of the predictive interpretations of the magnetometer images have been confirmed, and more importantly – they have been discovered previously unknown types of archaeological structures within the culture.

Figure 1: (A) Results of preliminary interpretation of the magnetometer survey. (B_top & bottom) Results of the verification of surveys by archaeological excavations.

Management Committee Meeting

(Hybrid meeting, [contact the organisers](#) to attend online)

DAY 3

Thursday 20th April 2023				
VENUE: Suhmhuset Auditorium				
9:00	9:30	Morning coffee		
9:30	09:45	Intro of the Day & LO communications		
Joint WG Meeting (Hybrid)				
<i>Topic 1: Emerging topics & future developments identified during the Action and that could potentially be addressed by future COST activities such as Actions S&T Conferences, Exploratory Workshops, or others</i>				
9:45	10:15	Each WG will gather to discuss Topic 1		
10:15	10:30	Plenary discussion on Topic 1		
<i>Topic 2: What are your ideas on how to sustain our network beyond 25 April 2023?</i>				
10:30	10:45	What are your ideas on how to sustain our network beyond 25 April 2023?		
10:45	11:00	Plenary discussion on Topic 2		
11:00	11:30	Coffee Break		
<i>Topic 3: SAGATHON 4 – Objective: Opening it to the public</i>				
11:30	11:40	Presentation by Jan Horak		
11:40	12:30	Work by DT sections: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Equipment: Andrei Asandulasei & Sebastiano D’Amico (coordinators) 2. Sites and Environmental data sources: Jan Horák & F-X Simon (coordinators) 3. Methods: Apostolos Sarris, Jörg Fassbinder & Mahmut Dragor (coordinators) 4. Funding & Library: Clare Wilson & Philippe De Smedt (coordinators) 		
12:30	14:00	Lunch		
MC Meeting (Hybrid)				
14:00	14:30	Agenda		

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verification of the presence of two-thirds of the Participating COST Countries 2. Agenda adoption 3. Approval of minutes and matters arising of last meeting 4. Update on activities, note on the implementation of COST policies & MoU objectives follow-up from the Action Chair (and other members of leadership, if required) 5. Update from the Science Communication Coordinator (Agnese Kukela) 6. Update from the Grant Holder: Action budget status (Ingrid Salvesen) 7. Update from the COST Association (Estelle Emeriau) 8. Action Plan beyond 25th April '023 (tasks left to complete/other initiatives?) Topics/Calls/SAGA Community Statement of Purpose 9. Any other Matter
14:30	15:00	Break
15:00	16:00	<p>MC meeting (continuation) and parallel sessions to discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • specific project proposals • SAGA Community Statement of Purpose • preps of the 3rd SAGA newsletter
16:00	16:30	LO Communications & Closing

This publication is based upon work from COST Action SAGA (CA17131), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, www.cost.eu). COST is a funding agency for research and innovation networks. COST Actions help connect research initiatives across Europe and enable scientists to grow their ideas by sharing them with their peers. The authors acknowledge the financial support provided by COST.

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